

ANALYSIS OF THE LABOR MARKET TO MEET THE DEMAND FOR HIGHLY QUALIFIED PERSONNEL.

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Abstract: *This article is aimed at training highly qualified personnel and increasing their role and importance in the labor market. The infrastructure of the market of specialist education services works to regulate the relationship between employers and employees on labour costs, working conditions, training and retraining of workers, protection of the rights of employees and consumers. The system of training specialists is one of the elements of the labour market infrastructure, which directly regulates supply and demand in the market.*

Keywords: *Higher education system, institution, quality, economy, human resource, market economy, expediency, efficiency, usefulness, labor market, flexibility, modernization.*

The infrastructure of the market of specialist education services works to regulate the relationship between employers and employees on labour costs, working conditions, training and retraining of workers, protection of the rights of employees and consumers. The system of training specialists is one of the elements of the labour market infrastructure, which directly regulates supply and demand in the market.

One of the problems of the country is the underdevelopment of infrastructure in the market of educational services for specialists. Creative groups of leading professors and representatives of enterprises at the specialized departments of higher education institutions serve as a mechanism for cooperation - a unique infrastructure in the labour market, which in turn is a key link in the organization of innovative cooperation. Creative groups collect a list of modern enterprises in accordance with the specialization of the department and detailed information about their activities. Studies, analyzes and systematizes the existing scientific and technological problems of each enterprise on the list. This will allow to mobilize the intellectual potential of the department to solve these problems and thus ensure the effectiveness of scientific research in higher education. As a result of such mutually beneficial cooperation both for the higher education

system and for production, on the one hand, the practice of training and production will be improved, the quality of education will increase, the practical knowledge and skills of teachers will be improved. nicknames are constantly updated, and potential employers are involved in the employment process of graduates.

On the other hand, in accordance with the real needs, the supply of highly qualified, competitive personnel will be established, a portfolio of investment projects on practical problems of enterprises will be formed, product quality improvement, cost reduction, transition of enterprises to innovative development. As a result of the work carried out in the country, a total of about 4,500 mature professors and scientists, graduate students, doctoral students and researchers, talented students, including more than 600 departments of higher education institutions, have been created. More than 750 innovation groups have been formed, consisting of representatives of industry, and a database of modern enterprises in accordance with the direction of the departments has been created. Appropriate work has been done to establish innovative corporate partnerships with about 1,200 of these enterprises on a contractual basis, and a bank of existing scientific and technological problems has been formed. These practical problems of enterprises serve as a basis for the formation of topics of graduate work, master's, candidate's and doctoral dissertations, scientific research on the basis of economic contracts, which are carried out at the departments since the new academic year. Such creative groups have been established at more than 40 departments of Bukhara State University and contracts have been signed with more than 200 enterprises. The work being done, in turn, requires improving the infrastructure.

It is necessary to further expand the market of educational services for specialists and organize and develop the activities of personnel agencies and various types of specialized labor exchanges, which collect information on the supply and demand in the labor market, work on decent employment. It would be appropriate for these agencies to focus on remote areas and rural areas.

It is known that the personnel agency is an independent organization that selects employees at the request of the employer. Applying to recruitment agencies is often ineffective, as resumes submitted by young professionals are sometimes ignored. This is due to the fact that many agencies are not adapted to work with young professionals and their resumes are kept with people who do not have work qualifications. The low demand for graduates is due not only to their low qualifications, but also to the fact that many companies do not have the principles of working with young professionals, and recruitment agencies do not provide such services.

The activities of regional personnel agencies are aimed at coordinating the interaction of universities in the region and public administration, helping professionals to find suitable positions in the labor market and forecasting the demand for specialists in the labor market. The solution to the problem of employment of specialists can be solved only in the coordination of relations between universities and regional enterprises, organizations and the formation of mutually beneficial relations.

One of the new organizational methods of interaction between higher education and industry is the Board of Trustees. Today, each higher education institution has a Board of Trustees. The Board of Trustees is a voluntary society, a non-profit organization, a public administration organization that wishes to assist in the training and retraining of specialists, the development of the scientific base, the social protection of students and staff. But at the moment, this opportunity is not fully used. The relationship of the institution with the Board of Trustees is directly related to the production of this institution. Through these contacts, the issues of student internships, the expansion of research, employment of young professionals can be addressed. Relationships should develop in a way that satisfies mutual interests.

As a result of our research, we came to the conclusion that in order to increase the professionalism of students in the market of educational services and their competitiveness in the labor market, a fund should be established to assist graduates in employment. The fund's work to help graduates find jobs is coordinated with the authorities and employment services. Employment assistance centers should develop comprehensive measures to regulate vocational education services in the labor market on the basis of current legislation. In our opinion, it is expedient that these measures include: annual analysis of the professional staff, monitoring the number of unemployed graduates and their employment; formation of a database on the structure of vacancies for young professionals; organization of contacts with employers in order to provide employment for graduates; Establishing relations with the regional authorities, the leadership of the university and the funds of educational institutions for the employment of graduates; planning requirements for young professionals in the regional economy; making suggestions for new emerging specialties.

The coverage of teachers with higher education in rural schools is 65%, while in urban areas it is about 95%. 126.4 thousand teachers (27.4%) working in schools of the republic do not have higher education, of which 16.4 thousand teachers (7.4%) have basic subjects - native language and literature, mathematics, physics, chemistry, history, basics of state and law, foreign language, geography, biology. The issue of providing primary school teachers remains relevant. Among them,

60-65% by region have higher education, although the foundation for a person's later life is laid at the age of primary school1.

The level of education and the status of the profession (job position) are compatible only if the supply and demand for skilled labor in the labor market are balanced. If the demand for skilled labor is higher than the supply of highly skilled workers, employers will be forced to fill existing jobs with less skilled labor than required. In this case, the professional requirements for the specialist will change.

One of the problems in the field of education is still the high demand of employers for specialists trained by higher education institutions for production, service and management systems. This problem has existed before, at the heart of which is the concept of specialization, and now at the heart of this term is the training of specialists and quality indicators based on the requirements of market relations.

The market for educational services to some extent reflects the socio-economic aspects of society that affect the adaptation and employment opportunities of university graduates. In this regard, as a subject of market relations, university graduates should be ready to look for jobs that meet the requirements of the labor market and employers.

A group of scholars classifies the strategy of behavior of university graduates in the market of educational services as follows:

- start work at the end of the study period;
- to continue studying;
- not to start "waiting" study or work;
- Spending free time with the family without starting work.

In the current situation, not only changes in the system of vocational training from a socio-psychological point of view have led to the selection of flexible specialties from narrow specialties and small responsibilities to a wide range of qualifications, but also to the selection of flexible professional skills. market movements have not yet been sufficiently studied.

REFERENCES:

1. Junaydulloyevich, A. A., Furqatovna, O. N., & Baxtiyorovich, A. B. (2021, March). Training highly qualified staff in development of uzbekistan. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 288-292).
2. Bakhodirovna, U. A., & Ilkhomovna, Z. M. (2021). Tourist potential of the Bukhara region. *Researchjet journal of analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 243-246.
3. Nizamov, A. B., & Gafurova, S. K. (2020). Assessment of factors influencing the quality of education in higher educational

institutions. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 1784-1796.

4. Khamidov, O. K. (2020). Foreign countries' experience in developing tourism potential and significance of clusters in Uzbekistan. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(2), 281-284.

5. Abdullayeva, H. (2021). Japanese Experience in Increasing the Efficiency of Tourist Territories in Uzbekistan. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 7(7).

6. Narzieva, D. M., & Kudratov, A. D. (2021). the importance of digitalization of the economy and priorities in Uzbekistan. *World Economics and Finance Bulletin*, 2(2), 9-13.

7. Navruz-zoda, Z. (2020). Evaluation of Holy Places of the Regions for the Development of Pilgrimage Tourism. *Indonesian Journal of Law and Economics Review*, 6, 10-21070.

8. Narzullayeva, G. S., & Sh, O. S. (2021). Theoretical aspects of assessment of marketing communications. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6, 3-3.

9. Agzamov, A. T., Rakhmatullaeva, F. M., & Giyazova, N. B. (2021, June). Marketing strategy for the competitiveness of modern enterprises. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 1-3).

10. Rakhmatullayeva, F. M., Boboyeva, G. G., & Kudratov, A. D. (2021). Essence of Structural Shifts in Regional Economic Systems. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(5), 128-130.

11. Abdulloev, A. J., Tairova, M. M., & Aminova, N. B. (2020). Manufacturing supply chain management development strategy. In *European research: innovation in science, education and technology* (pp. 25-27).

12. Yavmutov, D. S., & Rakhimov, O. H. (2021). Pilgrimage Tourism And Its Prospects In Uzbekistan. *Economics*, (1), 29-31.

13. Turobova, H. R., & Kodirov, A. A. (2016). The role of small businesses to improve the export potential. *Academy*, (12), 21-23.

14. Umarovna, T. M. (2021). A three-step strategy to develop the industrial economy in China through entrepreneurship and innovation. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(06), 152-156.

15. Furqatovna, O. N., Niyozovna, N. I., & Nutfulloyevna, A. H. (2022). Approaches Aimed At Ensuring a High Quality of Education in the Training of Economists. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 2(3), 78-83.

16. Muminov, K. I., & Abdullaeva, H. (2020). The effect of coronavirus pandemic to Uzbekistan tourism. *South Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research*, 10(11), 36-42.
17. Abdulloev, A. J., Tairova, M. M., & Aminova, N. B. Environmentally friendly and sustainable supply chain management in the platform economy.
18. Narzullayeva, G. S., & Odinayeva, N. F. (2021). Foreign Experience in Ensuring High Competitiveness of Economists in Higher Education. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(6), 155-160.
19. Hakimovna, U. M., & Muhammedrisaevna, T. M. S. (2022). Audit and Marketing Audit in Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship: The Order and Process of Inspection. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 2(3), 84-88.
20. Khalimova, N. J. (2022). Uzbekistan Hospitality Training Programs and its Problems. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 2(3), 57-66.
21. Tairova, M., Xurramov, O., & Odinaeva, N. (2021). An important role of internet marketing in digital tourism. *Центр научных публикаций (buxdu.uz)*, 5(5).
22. Odinayeva, N. F. (2021). Module-credit in the development of education system. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(06), 190-196.
23. Halimova, N. J., & Ismatillayeva, S. S. (2021, November). The Perspectives of Development Children Tourism in Uzbekistan. In *International Conference On Multidisciplinary Research And Innovative Technologies* (Vol. 2, pp. 184-188).
24. Qayimova, Z. A., & Aminova, N. B. (2021, October). Modern Interest Rate Policy of Commercial Banks. In "online-conferences" platform (pp. 259-263).